

Project Factsheet

TipESM: Exploring Tipping Points and their Impacts Using Earth System Models

Background

Anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases and land-use changes are warming the planet, reaching around 1.1°C above pre-industrial values. Despite efforts to reduce emissions, global warming relentlessly continues, increasing the likelihood of exceeding the warming targets of the Paris Agreement. According to the most recent IPCC 2023 report, limiting global warming to well below 2°C is becoming extremely challenging.

Even modest levels of warming put several Earth system phenomena at risk of reaching critical thresholds (tipping points), which, when exceeded, can lead to significant, abrupt, and potentially irreversible changes in entire ecosystems.

Researching tipping points in phenomena like the melting of West Antarctic and Greenland ice sheets, low-latitude coral reefs die-off, and permafrost thaw, among others, may result in severe, even catastrophic consequences for ecosystems, biodiversity and society.

Expected impacts of TipESM

The key objectives of the project are to:

- Advance knowledge and solutions in Earth system science, pathways to climate neutrality, climate change adaptation, climate services, social science for climate action and understanding of climate-ecosystem interactions
- Contribute substantially to key international assessments (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, and the European Environment Agency)
- Increase the transparency, robustness, trustworthiness and practical usability of the knowledge base on climate and Earth system change for use by policymakers, practitioners, other stakeholders and citizens
- Strengthen the European Research Area with increased knowledge of the risks of crossing climate tipping points

Project Snapshot

Duration: 1 January 2024 - 31 December 2027

Project Coordinator: Danish Meteorological Institute

Contact: Dr Shuting Yang (sy@dmi.dk)

Our approach

TipESM will deliver a step change in our understanding of climate tipping points in the Earth system, including their impact on ecosystems and society, combined with a set of early warning indicators and safe emission pathways that minimize the risk of exceeding such tipping points.

TipESM brings together scientists from a range of disciplines to contribute to six key areas:

- Simulating tipping points in the Earth system with the latest generation of Earth System Models
- Extending the knowledge of climate tipping points and their driving processes
- Understanding the risk for cascades of tipping points in the climate and ecosystems and defining early warning indicators
- Identifying climate change-driven tipping points in ecosystem and society
- Generating new knowledge on the impacts of tipping events on ecosystems and society
- Delivering a set of safe emissions pathways to minimize the risk of crossing tipping points

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UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

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How we work

The conceptual diagram of TipESM shows:

- the planned scientific work, and
- the dissemination and exploitation activities, which will run in parallel with the project and data management.

TipESM will also use observations and the existing WCRP Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP) archives to benchmark the TipESM simulations and develop methods for identifying the tipping points and early warning indicators.

Project partners and collaborations

Partners:

- Project coordinator: Danish Meteorological Institute
- Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
- The French National Centre for Scientific Research (and their affiliated entities)
- The Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute
- University of Bergen
- The Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research
- Barcelona Institute for Global Health

Associated partners

- University of Leeds
- Met Office UK
- University of Reading
- University of Liverpool
- University of Bern
- Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research

TipESM collaborates closely with the following initiatives and EU-funded projects:

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